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ASSESSMENT OF ANTIBIOTIC SENSITIVITY OF POULTRY DRUGS AMONG HOUSEHOLD AND BACKYARD CHICKEN FARMERS IN SOKOTO METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

The increasing global demand for poultry products has intensified the use of antibiotics in both commercial and backyard poultry production. This study assessed the types of antibiotics commonly used, knowledge of antimicrobial resistance, and patterns of drug administration among household and backyard poultry keepers in Sokoto metropolis, Nigeria. Data were collected through semi-structured questionnaires (n = 70 households) and supported with secondary data from three veterinary clinics (n = 412 case records, 2021–2023). Broilers were the most commonly reared chicken type (62.9%), followed by local chickens (24.2%) and layers (12.9%). Most respondents (77.1%) practiced intensive management systems, and 91.4% reported using antibiotics. The most frequently used drugs were Amoxycol (71.4%), Gentamicin (12.9%), Oxytetracycline (8.6%), Enrofloxacin (5.7%), and Neomycin (1.4%). While 82.9% of respondents consulted experts prior to administering antibiotics, 17.1% relied on self-administration or non-professional advice. Notably, 68.6% of respondents were aware of antimicrobial resistance, but only 22.9% observed withdrawal periods before selling or consuming poultry meat. The veterinary clinic data showed a similar reliance on Amoxycol (43.2%) and Oxytetracycline (23.3%) for poultry cases. The study highlights both the widespread use of antibiotics and critical gaps in stewardship, particularly regarding withdrawal period compliance. Strengthening farmer education, enforcing veterinary guidelines, and promoting responsible antibiotic use are essential to mitigate the risk of antimicrobial resistance.

KEYWORDS: Bacteria, poultry, questionnaire and antibiotics

INTRODUCTION

Poultry production is rapidly expanding in Nigeria and globally, playing a crucial role in income generation, employment creation, food security, and contributing to sociocultural, economic, and environmental sustainability (Hedman *et al.*, 2020). Globally, it is estimated that 16.2 billion birds are raised annually, producing over 67.7 million metric tons of chicken meat and 57.8 million metric tons of eggs (Hundie *et al.*, 2019). In Africa, village or traditional poultry systems contribute more than 70% of chicken products and supply around 20% of the continent's animal protein consumption (Kahin *et al.*, 2024). Approximately 99% of hens are raised in backyard or free-range systems, while only 1% are kept under intensive management (Hedman *et al.*, 2020).

In Nigeria, the poultry sector has shown significant growth, with an estimated 249 million birds nationwide as reported by Doris, (2023). A large segment of both rural and urban populations in northwestern Nigeria engage in poultry farming for subsistence and income generation. However, challenges persist particularly due to the involvement of untrained and unlicensed animal health providers, as well as unregulated access to antibiotics. This has led to the misuse of antimicrobials for disease prevention, treatment, and growth enhancement (Adesokan *et al.*, 2015; Ogwuche *et al.*, 2021).

Antibiotics are widely used in poultry farming not only for treating clinically ill birds but also as a preventive measure during periods of increased disease risk (McEwen and Fedorka-Cray, 2002; Sharma, 2024). Additionally, the use of antibiotics as prophylactics and growth enhancers remains a common practice in many poultry operations (Manyi-Loh *et al.*, 2018; Agyare *et al.*, 2018). Global antibiotic use in food-producing animals is projected to increase by 67% by 2030 (O'NEILL, 2015; Naghavi, 2022). Without timely and effective interventions, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) could result in an estimated 10 million deaths annually by 2050 (Afari-Asiedu *et al.*, 2020; Do *et al.*, 2021). Numerous studies worldwide have reported the frequent application of antibiotics in poultry production (Bashahun and Odoch, 2015; Mukasa *et al.*, 2012; Nayiga *et al.*, 2020). While antibiotics are often used to manage disease outbreaks, improper or indiscriminate use has led to the emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains, leaving birds increasingly susceptible to common infections. Given the growing public health and economic risks associated with antimicrobial-resistant pathogens, studies across Africa have documented high antibiotic use in poultry production, but little is known about practices in backyard and household poultry systems in Sokoto metropolis. This study was therefore designed to identify the commonly used antibiotics, farmers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding antibiotic use and AMR as well as compares findings with veterinary clinic prescription data to provide a more reliable picture of antibiotic use patterns in Sokoto metropolis, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

- **Study Area**

The area of study is Sokoto metropolis, The metropolis is made up of four local government areas (LGA) which included Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Part of Dange-Shuni and Wamakko. Sokoto (13°03'44"N 5°14'02"E) is a city located in the extreme northwest of Nigeria near the confluence of the Rima and Sokoto rivers. It has a land area of approximately 56,000 square kilometers. It is 308 meter above sea level, the state is bordered in the North by Niger Republic, Zamfara State to the East and Kebbi State to the South and West. It is thus one of the 36 states of Nigeria, located in the extreme northwest of the country. As of 2022 it has an estimated population of more than 6.3 million (Okeowo *et al.*, 2023)

- **Study Design**

The study was conducted in Sokoto metropolis, comprising four Local Government Areas (LGAs). A cross-sectional design was employed using a stratified multi-stage sampling approach. Semi-structured

questionnaires were administered to 70 households keeping backyard poultry. The questionnaire was used to collect data on socio-demographic characteristics, poultry types, management practices, and antibiotic use. The instrument was administered in English and translated into Hausa where necessary. Ethical approval was granted by Sokoto State University in collaboration with the Ministry of Animal Health and Fisheries Development. Secondary data were obtained from three major veterinary clinics (Arkillla, Runjin Sambo, and Sokoto Central) covering 2021–2023 poultry cases. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics with STATA v13.

RESULTS

Out of 70 respondents, an equal gender distribution was observed (50% male, 50% female). Adults constituted the majority (80%) as indicated in Table 1. Broilers (62.9%) were the most reared, followed by local chickens (24.2%) and layers (12.9%). Intensive management systems were dominant (77.1%). Among respondents, 91.4% reported antibiotic use, primarily Amoxycol, Gentamycin, Oxytetracycline, Enrofloxacin, and Neomycin. While most respondents consulted experts, 17.1% relied on informal advice or self-medication. Knowledge gaps were evident, with only 22.9% adhering to withdrawal periods. Secondary data from veterinary clinics (n = 412 cases) corroborated household findings, showing high use of Amoxycol (43.2%) and Oxytetracycline (23.3%) as shown in Table 5. In additionally, out of 70 participants interviewed, 68.57% were aware of antimicrobial drug resistance and 31.43% were observed to be unaware.

People with the knowledge of withdrawal period were found with the 81.42% as the highest followed by 18.58%. Not withstand, 54 (77.14%) of the respondents do not check or observe WP before selling or consuming poultry meat while only 22.86% were found to check WP respectively. Basically, 71.42% of the respondents were recorded to check the expiry date of the antibiotic before use while 28.57% reported that they do not as shown in Table 4. As indicated in, Fig. 1, participants from Arkilla were found to rear Broiler, followed by Low Cost, Dambuwa, and Tudun wada respectively. While Local chicken were observed to be the second chicken reared in the study with highest prevalence in two area namely Arkilla and Kasuwar dankure, thus layer chicken were reported as the least reared birds in the study in which Runji Sambo and Low cost had the lowest value of layer chicken.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Details of the Respondents

Social Group	Variable	No. of Respondent (n = 70)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	35	50
	Female	35	50
Maturity Status	Young	14	20
	Adult	56	80

Table 2: Knowledge of the Respondents with respect to Type of Chickens, Reared and Management in the Study areas

Chicken Type	No. of Respondents (n = 70)	Percentage (%)
Broiler	44	62.9
Layer	9	12.9
Local	17	24.2
System of Management		
Intensive	54	77.14
Free range	16	22.85
Do you give your chicken drug?		
Yes	64	91.42
No	6	8.57
Type of drug used		
Amoxycol	50	71.42
Oxytetracycline	6	8.57
Neomycin	1	1.42
Enrofloxacin	4	5.71
Gentamycin	9	12.85

Table 3: Drugs Administered to the Chickens based on Expertise Recommended in the Study Area

Do you consult expert before administering drugs to your poultry?	No. of Respondents (n = 70)	Percentage (%)
Yes	58	82.85
No	12	17.14
On whose instruction do you give drug(s) to your poultry?		
Veterinary Doctor	42	60
Animal Heath Attendant	14	20
Drug Seller	8	8.88
On your own	6	8.57
Are the drugs effective in your poultry?		
Yes	53	75.72
No	17	24.28

Table 4: Knowledge about the Drugs Resistance within the Respondents

Are you aware of antimicrobial drug resistance?	No. of Respondents (n = 70)	Percentage (%)
Yes	48	68.57
No	22	31.43
Are you aware of withdrawal period (WP) of drugs?		
Yes	57	81.42
No	13	18.58
Do you observe WP before selling/consuming poultry meat?		
YES	16	22.86
NO	54	77.14
Do you check the expiry date of drugs?		
YES	50	71.42
NO	20	28.57

Table 5: Antibiotics Prescribed in Veterinary Clinics in Sokoto Metropolis (2021–2023)

Antibiotic Prescribed	Number of Prescriptions (n=412 cases)	Percentage (%)	Common Indications
Amoxycol	178	43.2	Respiratory infections, enteritis
Oxytetracycline	96	23.3	Newcastle disease complications, CRD management
Gentamycin	54	13.1	Septicemia, bacterial enteritis
Enrofloxacin	47	11.4	Colibacillosis, fowl cholera
Neomycin	22	5.3	Diarrhea, gut infections
Others (erythromycin, tylosin)	15	3.6	Chronic respiratory infections

Fig. 1: Types of Chicken Reared Per Areas Surveyed

DISCUSSION

This study provides important insights into the patterns of antibiotic use, knowledge of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), and compliance with drug withdrawal periods among backyard poultry farmers in Sokoto metropolis. The findings indicate that antibiotic use is widespread (91.4%), with Amoxycol being the most frequently administered drug, both in household settings and veterinary clinic prescriptions. Although most respondents (82.9%) sought expert consultation before administering drugs, poor adherence to withdrawal periods (22.9%) and reliance on informal advice by a minority (17.1%) highlight significant gaps in antimicrobial stewardship. The high reliance on Amoxycol, Oxytetracycline, and Gentamycin reported in this study is consistent with findings from Uganda, where farmers frequently used tetracycline and macrolide derivatives (Nayiga *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, studies in Tanzania (Mubito *et al.*, 2014) and Ogun State, Nigeria (Oluwasile *et al.*, 2014), documented frequent antibiotic use on poultry farms, with usage rates approaching 100%. In Abia State, Nigeria, Amaechi (2014) found that 65% of poultry farms periodically administered antibiotics, a prevalence similar to our findings. The predominance of broilers (62.9%) among households in Sokoto is also consistent with observations in Zambia, where broiler production dominates poultry enterprises (Bronkhorst and Chongo, 2015).

Interestingly, this study found relatively high rates of veterinary consultation compared to earlier Nigerian studies by Okoli *et al.* (2002, 2005), where self-medication was widespread due to cost and limited veterinary access. The mixed approach in Sokoto where both trained animal health workers and farmers administer antimicrobials suggests gradual improvement in veterinary engagement, although gaps in professional oversight remain.

The dominance of intensive poultry management systems (77.1%) likely drives antibiotic reliance. Intensive systems are often associated with poor biosecurity (Standards and Testing, 2018), which predisposes flocks to disease outbreaks and necessitates antibiotic use (Conan *et al.*, 2013). In densely populated urban areas like Sokoto, increasing demand for poultry meat may further pressure farmers to use antibiotics not only for treatment but also for prophylaxis and growth enhancement. Similar drivers have been reported globally, where population growth, urbanization, and consumer demand have reshaped smallholder poultry farming into more commercialized operations heavily dependent on antimicrobials (Van Boeckel *et al.*, 2015). Although 68.6% of respondents were aware of AMR and 81.4% reported knowing about withdrawal periods, only 22.9% adhered to them in practice. This gap between knowledge and behavior mirrors findings from Ghana and Bangladesh, where farmers demonstrated awareness of AMR yet continued inappropriate practices due to economic pressures, limited regulatory enforcement, and perceived low risk (Nkansa *et al.*, 2020; Saiful *et al.*, 2016). Farmers in Sokoto may avoid observing withdrawal periods to meet urgent household needs or to prevent financial losses, inadvertently increasing the risk of antimicrobial residues in poultry products.

The widespread use of antimicrobials in backyard poultry poses significant public health risks. Drugs such as colistin, tylosin, and fluoroquinolones frequently reported in poultry farming are classified as critically important for human medicine by WHO (2019). The presence of antimicrobial residues in poultry meat and eggs due to non-compliance with withdrawal periods threatens consumer health and may contribute to the development of drug-resistant pathogens. Moreover, antimicrobial misuse in backyard systems, where biosecurity is weak, increases the likelihood of environmental contamination and zoonotic transmission of resistant bacteria (Manyi-Loh *et al.*, 2018; Hedman *et al.*, 2020).

The combination of household survey data with veterinary clinic prescription records provides a triangulation which enhances the reliability of findings by reducing reliance on self-reported practices

alone. However, the relatively small sample size (n = 70 households) limits the generalizability of the results. In addition, self-reported data may be affected by recall or social desirability bias, with some farmers potentially underreporting non-compliance with recommended practices.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the widespread use of antibiotics in backyard poultry farming in Sokoto metropolis, with Amoxycol being the most frequently used drug. While most farmers demonstrated some awareness of antimicrobial resistance and sought veterinary advice, poor adherence to withdrawal periods and continued reliance on non-expert guidance undermine responsible drug use. The convergence of household reports and veterinary clinic prescription data confirms the high dependence on a narrow range of antibiotics, raising concerns about antimicrobial residues in poultry products and the spread of resistant pathogens. To safeguard public health and ensure sustainable poultry production, interventions must focus on strengthening farmer education, enforcing veterinary regulations, and promoting biosecurity practices that reduce reliance on antibiotics. Addressing these gaps is critical for curbing antimicrobial resistance in both animal and human populations.

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